

Table 1. Data Sources in the Research

Data Type	Data Source	Data Description	Collection Method
Primary Data	Survey	Perceptions of administrators and educators regarding Big Data in academics.	Questionnaires for faculty and administrators.
	Semi-Structured Interview	Insights from institutional leaders on challenges and effectiveness.	Interviews with academic leaders and senior lecturers.
Secondary Data	Academic Records	Institutional archives (2019–2023) including Grades and GPA.	Academic management system.
	Student Attendance	Online and offline lecture attendance data.	Academic management system logs.
	E-learning Interactions	Student activities on online platforms (LMS) and login sessions.	Learning Management System (LMS) logs.
	Guidance History	Record of student interactions with academic supervisors.	Academic administration system.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix of Academic Factors and Success

Variables	GPA	Attendance	E-Learning Engagement	Advising Frequency
GPA	1.00	0.78	0.65	0.52
Attendance	0.78	1.00	0.45	0.30
E-Learning Engagement	0.65	0.45	1.00	0.38
Advising Frequency	0.52	0.30	0.38	1.00